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De novo drug design as a promising strategy in drug discovery and development

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Abstract

Looking back to the history of drug discovery a widespread concern about search for better quality hits and chemical leads have inspired the researchers for addressing the central challenge of drug design and development. Various techniques and in silico drug design approaches have been developed. Among these, de novo drug design approaches has been gain reputation for facilitating lead discovery. In current article, the role of de novo drug design strategy in drug design and development will be discussed.

Keywords: De novo strategy, drug design & development, drug design approaches, in silico drug design.